

LYRICAL EXPRESSION OF THE STAR IMAGE (BASED ON UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK POETRY)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15972617>

Abstract. This article explores the common imagery in the poetry of beloved Uzbek poets Erkin Vohidov and Abdulla Oripov, as well as Ibrayim Yusupov, a star of Karakalpak poetry. It analyzes the poems of these creators from two blood-related nations. The artistic similarities and unique features in the works of prominent Uzbek and Karakalpak artists are revealed through the example of the star image.

Keywords. Uzbek poetry, Karakalpak literature, lyrics, image, imagery, artistry, nationality, commonality, star, lyrical hero.

For centuries, literature has been performing the literary and aesthetic function of expressing human emotions, serving as a mirror of the soul, singing about pain and joy, and capturing them in written lines. In this regard, literature, as a form of art, has been refined and developed over the centuries. According to Ulugbek Hamdam: ..."Now the poet has turned his gaze inward from the outside - from the world-changing events happening around him - to his humble heart and began to 'translate' it." Indeed, the poet looks at the world from a unique perspective and expresses his feelings in lyrical lines. "True lyrical poetry," writes Hegel, "like any other genuine poetry, must express the true content of the human heart. However, everything, even the most objective and material phenomena, when acquiring lyrical content, must be personally felt, woven into the mirror of the soul, imagined, and contemplated." The poet expresses the world before his eyes using words that no one has spoken before, through images that have never been written about, and this demonstrates the poet's skill. "The artistic image depicted in a literary work is not only the result of generalization but also a product of concretization and individualization. After all, the literary hero must be truly individualized. The writer concretizes the artistic image by showing its individual characteristics, giving the image vitality, liveliness, naturalness, imbuing it with emotion - influencing the reader's feelings and convincing them," writes literary critic T. Boboyev. Similarly, in poetry, the images created by the poet enhance the impact of the poetic lines. In poetry, imagery manifests itself mainly through expressiveness and visual representation. Often these aspects coexist, intermingle, and merge with each other. Spontaneously inspired experiences - images create expressiveness, while

imagery, as mentioned earlier, is the result of long searches, experiments, and creative struggles. The world is so vast, so rich, and life is so colorful that there is always a theme for poetry. However, the inspiration and material for these poems must come from existence itself. All the images reflected in the work of the poet Abdulla Oripov, who was gifted with inspiration and talent by such existence, are artistically complete images. The scope of images in the poet's work is so vast

It is so diverse that it seems there is no topic left in life that the creator hasn't written about, and the resulting system of images itself is a small world. The images in Abdulla Oripov's poetry hold an important place in our literature due to their attractiveness, expression of Eastern traditions, national spirit, depth, multiple meanings, and

the weight and significance of the "burdens" placed on them. These images encompass everything from the smallest particles of nature and the deepest human feelings to universal problems. For example, in the poet's poetry, one can observe the use of the image of a star for various purposes. In particular, in the poet's poem "My Mother, Poetry," he compares poetry to a bright star that illuminates his path. The poet, who considered poetry the meaning of his life, also indicates that it filled his entire life with light.

You became my companion
On any day,
You became a bright star
In the darkest nights,
We conversed sometimes joyfully,
Sometimes in melancholic tones
My highest happiness,
My dear, poetry.
My found crown and throne,
My dearest, poetry.

In A.Oripov's poem "Tiny Star," which is well-known and beloved by all poetry enthusiasts, we can observe an extraordinarily unique simile. It's as if the poet is alluding to the time when he first ventured into poetry. Comparing the world of poetry to the dome of the sky, he likens himself to a flickering star and laments his loneliness. He sees no stars, no clouds, nor fog around him. We can observe how he compares himself to a candle, gazing at the shining stars of poetry.

On one edge of the blue dome,

Knocking its head against the void,
A tiny star flickers,
Shedding tears in solitude.
Around it, not a single star,
No cloud, no fog to be seen.
Gazing at the stars,
It trembles like a candle.

The poetry of Erkin Vohidov, a cherished poet of Uzbek literature, can be likened to a poetic ocean, distinguished by its elegance, artistic charm, a world of deep meaning infused with philosophy, and uniqueness in rhythm. In the poet's works, one can also observe the distinctive expression of the star image. For instance, in the poet's poem "Star," one can notice a unique simile. Sometimes, when he couldn't find a title for his poems, he would use a star symbol, intending to guard it day and night, hoping that the poetic lines he created would continue to shine even when his own star faded.

Sometimes, unable to find a title
I place a star above my poem.
Let it stand guard at the head of my poem
That star, day and night.
Let it shine like Venus
When I close my eyes at night.
May it never fade, may it shine brightly,
Even when it fades, it's my star.

The lyrical legacy of Ibrayim Yusupov, a star of Karakalpak poetry, stands out from his contemporaries due to the allure of its imagery. In the poet's works, we can witness the use of the star motif with various meanings. Particularly, in the following poetic lines, the poet compares his heart to the sky and likens his dreams and aspirations to stars. He suggests that the stars in his heart's sky are renewed monthly, and his thoughts have taken on different hues, indicating he has ceased harboring unattainable wishes in his heart.

Stars fade in my heart's sky,
The moon has ceased its waxing.
Thoughts turn to different melodies,
Dreams of what could have been are abandoned.

In another poem by the poet, the lyrical hero, intoxicated by his beloved's joy, expresses feeling as if he's wandering among the moon and stars in the sky.

He adds that if she's upset, he develops his thoughts by saying he feels terrible and sick even when he's healthy.

When you rejoice, my heart overflows,
I wander among the moon and stars.
If you're slightly upset, I feel ill,
I wound my healthy soul

In a subsequent poem, I. Yusupov uses the star image in its literal sense and expresses pride in his era. The poet strengthens his thoughts by stating that the people of his time take pride in flying to the moon and stars, that they have uncovered the secrets of the atom, and that they are astounded by its power.

My era has flown to the moon and stars,
It has discovered the powerful secrets of the atom.
That secret which it uncovered with its own mind,
Unable to turn back, he lost his mind.

In conclusion, it can be said that Abdulla Oripov, Erkin Vohidov, and Ibrayim Yusupov are major representatives of modern Uzbek and Karakalpak poetry. When they use a certain image in their poems, we witness that they imbue it with completely new facets of meaning, elevating it to the level of an artistic discovery. In particular, the symbol of the star used in the lyrics of these poets carries such significance.

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